

FASHION RECOMMENDATIONS BASED ON BODY SHAPES

Agnes Benny
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, Kerala, India
agnesbenny@mca.ajce.in

Sr. Mercy Joseph
Master of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, Kerala, India
elsinchakkalackal@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract:-A vital component of living is clothing. Making selections about what to wear is a tedious undertaking for everyone.

Dressing for the body shape, or being aware of one's body type and choosing the kind of clothing that would highlight the body's attributes, is a crucial style tip. The user's basic body form has never been taken into account by any several fashion suggestion algorithms for clothing items. I offer a methodology for analyzing data to determine how clothing trends and body types are associated and to advise a user on what to dress based on major physical characteristics. The experimental findings reveal a novel component of fashion advice.

Keywords:-Fashion analysis; recommender system; human body shape; clothing style; correlation; deep learning; Information extraction, recommender systems, and personalization

- **Round (apple shape)**
full bust and full hips without waist definitions
- ✂ **Hourglass**
full bust and full hips with waist definition
- ▼ **Inverted triangle (strawberry shape)**
broad shoulders and small bust
- **Rectangle (banana shape)**
straight up and down proportions with very little waist definitions
- ▲ **Triangle (pear shape)**
broader hips than shoulders

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, using fashion to express oneself is popular. It has always been a part of human nature to display one's social standing. Each individual is different in numerous ways, including their size, body type, color, and many others. As a

result, people must select clothing that is appropriate for them in light of these many factors. A person needs to dress well to make a good impression, stand out from the crowd, and appear presentable. As a result, it is crucial to consider outfit choices.

The body shape should be considered before choosing a suitable clothing style. The ratios between body measurements are especially important in establishing the body shape. A variety of images are employed to convey the types of body shapes, including fruit shapes, alphabetical letters (the apple, represents a body shape with a wide torso, broad shoulders, and full bust, waist, and upper back), geometric objects, and images of human anatomy (e.g., the top hourglass for a body shape with a well-defined waist and larger bust than hips).

The five fundamental body forms are the most prevalent. Body shape calculators available are based on subjective measurements and identifying the different body shapes remains an analytical problem. In determining body shape, the ratios between body measures are particularly crucial. Body shapes are represented by a variety of images such as fruit shapes, alphabetical letters (the apple for a wide torso, broad shoulders, and full bust, waist, and upper back), geometric objects, and pictures of human anatomy (the top hourglass for a body shape with a wide bust, waist, and upper back).

We can determine the ideal style after determining the body shape. It is difficult to know how to dress a particular body shape and balance the physical qualities when there are many restrictions, guidelines, and style disasters to avoid.

OBJECTIVES

In the proposed study, enhanced fashion recommendation systems are created utilizing pre-trained models that make recommendations based on the customer's body type.

The following goals are associated with the contribution to the suggested work:

- The measurements of the customer's body are used to determine their body silhouette.
- To provide the consumer with an acceptable piece of clothing, categorization of various clothing types according to body types.

- To classify data using both conventional and previously trained models.

other physical features, inter-compatibility of recommended items, etc

CONCEPT AND METHODOLOGY

For the goal of renting, the recommender system suggests the outfits to the female clients. The activities a user wishes to do, such as vacations, meetings, weddings, dates, etc., determine the renting purposes. The suggestion is based on characteristics like height, weight, bust size, body type, age, and purpose for renting clients. Given that a consumer might not be aware of their body type, we are assuming it for our computation.

Using information about a customer's height, weight, bust size, and age, Random Forest Classifiers are used to forecast the customer's body type. The goal is to classify people based on their anticipated body types and rental. To recommend the garments to our consumers based on the ratings of the most comparable user, we utilize collaborative filtering on them. The purpose of making clothing recommendations is to enhance the purchasing experience for clients and maintain the current fashion trend.

As we move forward with the implementation, the raw data provided by the customers were made up of categorical values that were transformed into numerical numbers for calculations. Customer records with missing values in numerical data are handled using mean-mode imputation. However, categorical information with omitted values is dealt with by binning approach, which is used across all dataset features. By dealing with the missing values and preventing the dimensionality reduction problem, the data is maintained in this way.

LITERATURE SURVEY

- Shintami Chusnul Hidayati, Cheng-Chun Hsu, Yu-Ting Chang, Kai-Lung Hua, Jianlong Fu, and Wen-Huang Cheng. What dress fits me best? Fashion Recommendation on the Clothing Style for Personal Body Shape. To recommend dresses according to body shapes by finding body shapes from the given measurements, and matching them with the available categories of dresses.
- Seema Wazarkar, Shruti Patil, Pratik S. Gupta, Kriti Singh, Mukund Khandelwal, C. V. Sri Vaishnav and Ketan Kotecha. Advanced Fashion Recommendation System for Different Body Types using Deep Learning Models. To address the issues of personalization and the subjectiveness of fashion recommendation by making the recommendation user-centric by taking into account the user's body type,

- Mst. Digant Pramod Garude, Ms. Anushree Khopkar, Ms. Monali Dhake, Ms. Shivani Laghane, and Mrs. Tabassum Maktum. Skin-tone And Occasion-Oriented Outfit Recommendation System. To provide suggestions on outfits based on one's skin-tone color, occasion, current trends, sizes, etc.
- Rahmadi Kurnia, Meza Silvana, and Ikhwana Elfitri. A Skin and Clothes Matching Seeded by Color System Selection. To determine the relationship between skin color and clothes color fuzzy logic rules were used.
- Marwa Jmal, Wided Souidene Mseddi, Rabah Attia, and Anis Youssef. Classification of Human Skin Color and its Application to Face Recognition. To classify a face into its possible skin color tone.

1. PROPOSED WORK

As previously noted, identifying body shape is the first step in learning how to dress in a way that makes a body appear its best. Existing body form calculators are highly subjective. The use of unsupervised learning algorithms to identify the "natural" grouping(s) of a set of body measures is a promising approach for identifying the type of body shape. We can see that clustering can be considered a solution to this issue.

Formally, clustering seeks to produce a suitable classification of the n body forms into various types given a collection of body shapes, each of which is represented by a set of body measurement data. The necessity for a clustering method that does not need to choose the number of clusters is related to the need to determine the many types of body forms, even if there are many methods accessible to do clustering.

1.1 System Design & Implementation Details

Mean-Mode Imputation is used for data pre-processing to handle missing values in numerical and categorical data. For features with categorical data, binning is also used to handle missing values, convert data into numerical representation, and handle missing values.

The Random Forest Classifier algorithm, which is trained on characteristics including age, bust size, size, height, and weight, is used to categorize and forecast the body types of clients. The hyperparameter known as is used for parameter tweaking.

With 'n-estimators' (i.e., tree size) = 100, the best prediction outcome was obtained. Given the userid and itemid, the Singular Vector Decomposition (SVD) algorithm predicts customer ratings for collaborative filtering, from which the highly rated cloth type is recommended. With these parameters, SVD produced the best results: n-factors=200 and n-epochs=50

1.2 System Workflow

- Bust sizes have been separated into Bust and Cup sizes. The NaN values are handled by taking the mode of Bust Size falling under Age bins.
- Height in 'feet and inches' are converted into 'centimeters'. Mean values were applied for missing values.
- As for Weight, 'lbs' were trimmed, and the Mean was applied for the missing values.
- Missing values in the 'Rented for' field was filled with 'other'.
- Missing values were handled by applying mode on the grouped 'Bust_size'.

Similar pre-processing is also done on the testing dataset and unrelated columns are dropped. The following fields are kept after pre-processing in the training set: Age, Body Type, Bust Size, Cup Size, Height, Size, and Weight. The following fields are kept after pre-processing in the testing dataset: Age, bust_size, Cup_Size, Size, Height, Weight, Rented_For, and User_id.

The model is trained on these values.

Body Type is predicted using Random Forest Classifier Algorithm. The users are grouped by 'Rented for' and Body Type. Using Singular Vector Decomposition (SVD), the rating for each Item_id is trained and predicted. After the process, an item is recommended from the highest-rated category that matches a body type.

1.3 Experiments / Evaluation

Train-test split:

We divided the dataset into an 80:20 ratio, which produced the best results when compared to the 70:30 and 60:40 ratios.

Classification method:

Based on customer body measurements, we used the Random Forest classifier to estimate the customer's "body type." KNN classifier and a logistic regression model were also tested. Among these, Random Forest provided the best score.

Random Forest parameter tuning:

Grouping: We grouped data instances based on the "body type" and "rented for" attributes using the data frame's groupby method. We reduced the number of dimensions in this way.

Collaborative filtering:

We used the SVD algorithm and the surprise library to forecast customer ratings for each item. We tested the SVD, KNN, and baseline algorithms, and the SVD performed better than any of them.

The dataset comprises fields fit, user_id, bust_size, item_id, weight, rating, rented for, review_text, body_type, review_summary, category, height, size, age, and review_date. The data is stored in a JSON file, which is read and then split into a training dataset with 80% of the data and a testing dataset with 20% of the data. The data is pre-processed.

Pre-processing

- Sequential bins of Age are created.

SVD parameter tuning:

The n factors and n epoch parameters of the SVD algorithm were tweaked for various values, but for the final prediction, we kept n factors=200 and n epochs=50.

- We can observe RMSE values for various parameter combinations on the graph with the title "SVD," and we conclude that the SVD performs at its best when n factors=200 and n-epochs=100.
- From the graph with the title 'KNN', we can see RMSE values obtained for different combinations of parameters, and consequently, we conclude that KNN works best when similarity is Pearson coefficient and the value of k does not affect performance.
- We can see RMSE values for various parameter combinations on the graph with the title "Baseline," and we get the conclusion that Baseline provides consistent performance for method ALS and variable performance for SGD.
- We can see that SVD outperforms all three collaborative filtering methods when we compare them. As a result, we employed SVD to predict ratings.
- We picked test size=0.25 as the default test size for our project because the graph with the caption "test size comparison" shows that all classifiers maintain constant performance in any way splitting the train-test dataset.
- We conclude that all classifiers exhibit increased accuracy if mean-mode imputation is used for missing values rather than removal from the

graph with the title "managing missing values".

- We deduce that the Random Forest classifier beats all other classifiers using graphs with the titles "test size comparison" and "managing missing values," and we, therefore, employed the Random Forest classifier technique to predict "body type."

1.4 Discussions

The data that was provided was not clean and so it was pre-processed. More than 14000 entries had missing bust size information throughout the preparation procedure. One of the key determinants of body type was this column. Therefore, by binning the data, we choose to impute those values based on age.

The first goal following pre-processing was to determine a person's body type based on their height, weight, and bust size. Although the body type of the person which was already in the database could be utilized, it was opted to use the classifier instead because people's body types can change. Therefore, supervised learning (machine learning) techniques were employed.

Finally, providing recommendations to the user was our primary goal. We, therefore, used collaborative filtering. We tested the SVD, KNN, and baseline algorithms for this. Then, after examining the data produced by various algorithms, we found that SVD worked well, therefore we put the finishing touches on the SVD method.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

To comprehend fashion style guidelines more fully, a graphic overview of clothing designs is necessary. In this study, we developed scalable models that record the semantic relationship between style trends and physical characteristics. Two inquiries regarding fashion styling advice can be answered using the data analysis models that have been developed: (1) What types of clothing fit a particular human body measurement the best? and (2) whatever type of body shape is best for a particular piece of clothing?

Future research on several issues is still possible. It is possible to implement innovative applications like customized recommendations. The system can recommend the most fashionable and well-fitting

Fashion Recommendation Based on Body Types

everyday clothing with the help of additional personal information from the user such as skin color. Additionally, we may implement online product retrieval using our suggestion results as a guide, which will significantly improve customers' purchasing experiences.

REFERENCES

- [1] Shintami Chusnul Hidayati, Cheng-Chun Hsu, Yu-Ting Chang, Kai-Lung Hua, Jianlong Fu, and Wen-Huang Cheng. What dress fits me best? Fashion Recommendation on the Clothing Style for Personal Body Shape.
- [2] Seema Wazarkar, Shruti Patil, Pratik S. Gupta, Kriti Singh, Mukund Khandelwal, C. V. Sri Vaishnav and Ketan Kotecha. Advanced Fashion Recommendation System for Different Body Types using Deep Learning Models.
- [3] Mst. Digant Pramod Garude, Ms. Anushree Khopkar, Ms. Monali Dhake, Ms. Shivani Laghane, and Mrs. Tabassum Maktum. Skin-tone And Occasion-Oriented Outfit Recommendation System. Cherene Francis. [n. d.]. Body Shape Calculator. <https://auraimageconsulting.com/body-shape-calculator/>. Accessed: 2017-08-21.
- [4] Rahmadi Kurnia, Meza Silvana, and Ikhwana Elfritri. A Skin and Clothes Matching Seeded by Color System Selection.
- [5] Marwa Jmal, Wided Soudiene Mseddi, Rabah Attia, and Anis Youssef. Classification of Human Skin Color and its Application to Face Recognition. To classify a face into its possible skin color tone.
- [6] GloablInfoResearch: Global Fast Fashion Apparel Market 2021 by Key Countries, Companies, Type, and Application. GloablInfoResearch, HongKong, 2021.
- [7] Hou, M., Wu, L., Chen, E., Li, Z., Zheng, V. W., & Liu, Q.: Explainable fashion recommendation: A semantic attribute region guided approach. In Proceedings of the 28th Twenty-Eighth International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence, 2019; pp. 4681- 4688.
- [8] Hidayati, S. C., Hsu, C. C., Chang, Y. T., Hua, K. L., Fu, J., & Cheng, W. H.: What Dress Fits Me Best? Fashion Recommendation on the Clothing Style for Personal Body Shape. In Proceedings of the 26th ACM International Conference on Multimedia (MM '18). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2018; pp. 438-446.
- [9] Wang, H., Wang, N., & Yeung, D. Y.: Collaborative Deep Learning for Recommender Systems. In Proceedings of the 21st CM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, New York, 2015; pp. 1235-1244.